

Energy Efficiency in Next-generation Optical Networks

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ABSTRACT Energy consumption in optical network infrastructures is investigated to identify energy-hungry key components and network functionalities. Solutions based on smart coherent pluggables are presented to increase energy efficiency at the edge of the metro segment.

Keywords: Energy consumption, energy efficiency, CO₂, smart pluggables, digital sub-carrier multiplexing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Communications networks play a crucial role in our daily lives, connecting an increasing number of people, areas, machines and providing a growing range of services. The COVID-19 pandemic has further stressed the importance of connectivity, e.g. for remote work. Experts predict that traffic will continue to increase at a rate exceeding 20% annually [1]. However, the information and communications technology (ICT) sector is responsible for between 5-9% of the global electricity usage [2] and contributes to around 3% of global greenhouse gas emissions, which is comparable to the emissions of the global airline industry [3]. NASA has warned that the concentration of carbon dioxide (CO₂) in the atmosphere has reached unprecedented levels, measuring around 420 parts per million in 2021 at the Mauna Loa Observatory in Hawaii and is steadily increasing [4]. These levels exceed those of the past 400,000 years, with CO₂ levels hovering around 200 parts per million during ice ages and around 280 ppm during warmer interglacial periods. In addition, global temperatures are rising, with 2020 tying with 2016 as the hottest year on record since 1880 [5]. Aside from the environmental impact, economic factors should also be considered. The ongoing conflict in Ukraine has resulted in a surge in energy prices, with oil, coal, and gas prices increasing by around 40%, 130%, and 180% respectively within the first two weeks of the invasion [6]. This increase in gas prices has also led to an upsurge in wholesale electricity prices in the Eurozone, with prices continuing to rise [7].

Given these challenges, it is imperative to explore solutions to reduce the power consumption and carbon footprint of global network infrastructures, as well as limit energy expenditure. This paper will investigate energy consumption in optical network infrastructures. Then, the potential of smart coherent pluggables with digital sub-carrier multiplexing (DSCM) to reduce the energy consumption of traffic aggregation at the edge of metro networks is presented.

2. ENERGY CONSUMPTION IN CURRENT NETWORKS AND RELATED LITERATURE

Optical technology carrying ultra-high data-rate traffic and connections provides large bandwidth while requiring components, such as optical switches, whose power consumption increases much less rapidly with the growing of exchanged data than similar employed electronic devices [8]. Transceivers (and transponders) utilize power-hungry digital-to-analog and analog-to-digital converters (DAC and ADC), and electronic application-specific integrated circuits (ASICs) to perform digital signal processing (DSP). Traditionally, DSP has been designed to meet transmission requirements rather than to optimize energy consumption. In addition, the power consumption of these devices increases with the symbol rate, which must grow to accommodate higher-speed traffic. Moreover, we have to consider that where different domains are connected (e.g., at the edge of metro/access segments), traffic is aggregated at the electronic domain (e.g., at the IP layer), thus relying on power-hungry electronic interfaces and processing. As an example, the work in [9] assumes several traffic aggregation scenarios at the edge: e.g. A) 2×100G, where half of the traffic is related to the access (as several flows at 10G) and the other half to the data center inter-connections, all aggregated at Layer 3; B) a similar scenario of (A) with the aggregation carried out by 2× Layer2/Layer3 switches; the related power consumption values can reach 2000 W for the former scenario and 400 W for the latter. Thus, traffic aggregation is a very important functionality impacting the overall network power consumption.

In the literature, researchers have investigated strategies to reduce power consumption in optical networks. These strategies can be classified into two main categories [10]: (1) *energy-proportional* strategies that adapt the speed of individual devices to the actual load and (2) *sleep mode* strategies – similar to the start&stop system of cars – that put idle devices at a negligible-power state. Regarding energy proportional strategies, current flexible transceivers already support multiple rates, thus providing an adaptation of their capacity to the traffic load [11], [12]. Sleep mode is particularly interesting since traffic presents large fluctuations during 24 hours, decreasing even by 50-60% at night [13]. Therefore, it is possible to re-route traffic within the network and nodes to reduce the number of used devices and to switch off (in sleep mode) the unused devices [14].

Figure 1: (a) P2P and electronic aggregation; (b) P2MP and optical aggregation with DSCM.

Figure 2: Network topology and traffic matrix.

However, to achieve greater energy efficiency in the short and medium term, infrastructures need to employ a wider use of optical technology. Many network functionalities that are currently performed mainly in electronics, such as traffic aggregation (see Fig. 1(a)), could consume much less power if performed in the optical domain, which is much more scalable with traffic load. Therefore, research must go beyond the two paradigms of energy-saving mentioned above to leverage other possibilities.

3. TRAFFIC AGGREGATION BASED ON DIGITAL SUB-CARRIER MULTIPLEXING

In this paper, we suggest a new approach to reduce energy usage in the metro segment by utilizing a novel metro edge node architecture called Point to Multipoint (P2MP) [15]. The P2MP architecture utilizes the Digital Sub-Carrier Multiplexing (DSCM) transmission technique, which adds an extra layer of multiplexing over Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM) by allowing several digital sub-carriers to be multiplexed over a wavelength channel [16]. The key point of this technology is that the digital sub-carriers can be all-optically multiplexed. This optical aggregation can replace electronic traffic aggregation typically used at the metro edge, reducing the use of power-intensive interfaces in favor of passive optical devices that consume negligible power.

Fig. 1(a) shows a traditional edge node architecture, in which point-to-point (P2P) low-rate connectivities (e.g., at 10 Gb/s) serve metro and accesses or data centers (DCs); at the edge, traffic is electronically aggregated flowing in the metro segment through higher-rate transceivers (e.g., at 100 Gb/s).

Fig. 1(b) shows a P2MP architecture where a passive optical splitter/coupler is connected to several transceivers at the access networks or DCs; in this case, transceivers support DSCM, thus different digital sub-carriers at the same wavelength channel are aggregated through the passive splitter/coupler, then injected in the metro links. Energy saving is achieved by two factors: saving several transceivers at the edge and realizing aggregation by passive optical devices. Although both cost and energy saving can be achieved with P2MP and DSCM, the following constraints should be taken into account: 1) the DSCM channel in the metro is subject to higher physical-layer degradation since the signals transparently cover an additional distance in the access segment, while in Fig. 1(a) the high-rate optical signal is confined only within the metro; 2) the sub-carriers composing the DSCM signal should be contiguous and detected at the same destination node in order to properly demultiplex the sub-carriers.

TABLE I: Power consumption [W].

	Short-		Medium-		Long-term	
	S ₁	S ₂	S ₁	S ₂	S ₁	S ₂
P2P	1008	540	1008	540	1212	540
P2MP	654	300	804	330	1056	360

4. SIMULATION RESULTS

The considered scenario for the performance analysis is shown in Fig. 2, where A and B are hubs (i.e., edge nodes) and the circles are leaf nodes (i.e., nodes in the access). More details on the topology can be found in [17]. The figure also shows projections of the traffic increase at the short-, medium-, and long-term. First, the number of interfaces (i.e., transceivers) is evaluated considering P2MP or P2P with traditional electronic aggregation. Several interfaces (or transceivers) are taken into account: 100Gb/s, 200Gb/s, and, in the case of P2MP, also XR pluggables that support a maximum rate of 400 Gb/s. With P2MP, all interfaces support DSCM, while with electronic aggregation they do not. Results are reported in Fig. 3. P2MP strongly reduces the number of interfaces for any projection at the short-, medium-, and long-term. For example, at the short-term, P2MP requires 20 interfaces in the considered scenario, while P2P requires 36 interfaces; at the long term P2MP requires around 24 interfaces, while electronic aggregation around 36.

The reduction of interfaces with P2MP translates to power savings. To analyse the power savings, the following two power consumption scenarios are taken into account: S₁) the power consumption of 100G is 28 W [18], 45 W for 200G [19], and 75 W for 400G (computed as interpolation of the previous ones); S₂) all transceivers are assumed to be comparable in terms of power consumption to the 400G ZR+ consuming 15 W [20]. The two S₁) and S₁) scenarios aim to emulate two conditions: when power consumption increases with bit rate and when power consumption at the different bit rate values is comparable.

The power consumption in the two scenarios is shown in Tab. I and has been computed considering the number of 100G, 200G, and XR interfaces in the three traffic projections conditions. Given that overall P2MP reduces the number of transceiver interfaces, relevant energy savings can be achieved with P2MP with respect to traditional network architecture where, in the edge node, opto-electronic conversion is performed. As an example, in the short term, in scenario S₁) (where power consumption increases with bit-rate interfaces), P2MP reduces power by 35%, while in scenario S₂) (where power consumption does not strongly depend on the bit rate) by 44%. In the long term, in scenario S₁), P2MP reduces power by 13%, while in scenario S₂) by 33%. Note that these numbers only account for transceiver interfaces, while electronic traffic aggregation in the traditional case is not reported. As an example, the power consumption of an IP router can be in the order of thousands of Watts [21], with the potential for P2MP to further reduce power consumption.

Figure 3: Number of required interfaces vs. traffic projections for electronic P2P aggregation (left) and P2MP aggregation (right).

5. CONCLUSION

This paper investigated the possibilities of P2MP and digital sub-carrier multiplexing in reducing power consumption of metro/access segments. P2MP, thanks to all-optical traffic aggregation enabled by digital sub-carriers, can reduce the number of transceivers in the network, and consequently the power consumption, by around 40%.

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